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LEVEL OF AWARENESS AMONG ADOLESCENT GIRLS ABOUT GENITAL INFECTIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON GYNECOLOGICAL HEALTH (RESEARCH RESULTS)

Abstract:

Genital infections are one of the most common problems in adolescence, which directly affects the state of gynecological and reproductive health. The insufficient level of awareness among adolescent girls about the causes, symptoms and possible consequences of these infections complicates early detection and timely treatment, which increases the risks of developing chronic gynecological diseases, infertility and oncological processes. The aim of this study was to assess the level of awareness of girls aged 13–18 years about genital infections, their impact on gynecological health, as well as to determine the attitude towards preventive measures, in particular vaccination against human papillomavirus (HPV). The study included 96 adolescent girls who anonymously filled out a questionnaire that included questions about knowledge about genital infections, symptoms, complications, preventive measures and awareness of HPV and vaccination. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the results, and data processing was carried out using Microsoft Excel.

Keywords: *genital infections, gynecological health, adolescents, awareness, symptoms, prevention, vaccination, HPV, reproductive health, risk factors, medical examinations, educational programs.*

Introduction

Reproductive health in adolescents is one of the key aspects of the modern healthcare system. [1] Genital infections, which remain a common problem among young people, require special attention, largely due to insufficient awareness and late seeking medical care. [2] Early sexual activity, lack of knowledge about

preventive measures, as well as stigmatization of topics related to intimate health, contribute to the development of complications that can negatively affect the reproductive future. [3]

Socio-demographic characteristics of participants

According to the results of the questionnaire, the distribution of respondents by age was as follows:

Age	Percentage (%)	Number of participants
13 years	10.42%	10
14 years	11.46%	11
15 years	18.75%	18
16 years	29.17%	28
17 years	11.46%	11

Sexual experience was reported by 46 out of 96 surveyed girls, accounting for 47.9% of the total sample. Analysis by age groups shows an increase in the frequency of sexual experience with age:

- Among girls aged 13-14 years, 28.6% (6 out of 21) had sexual experience.
- In the 15-16 age group, 45.7% (21 out of 46) reported sexual activity.
- The highest rate is observed in the 17-18 age group, where 65.5% (19 out of 29) of respondents have sexual experience.

These data indicate an early initiation of sexual activity among some adolescents, highlighting the need to strengthen preventive measures and increase sexual education, focusing on safe behavior, awareness of genital infections, and preventive strategies.

In addition to analyzing age and sexual experience, it was important to investigate the level of awareness of girls about the signs of possible diseases.

This allows us to understand how attentive the respondents are to their health and whether they are able to recognize symptoms that may indicate the presence of infections. In particular, 43% of respondents (42 people) noted that they notice changes in the nature of discharge from the genitals, such as color, odor, or consistency. This indicates a certain alertness and attentiveness to their own condition, but 46% (44 people) do not pay attention to this at all, and another 11% (10 people) answered “I don’t know”, which probably indicates an insufficient level of knowledge or lack of experience in self-examination.

A similar situation is observed regarding symptoms such as itching, pain, or discomfort in the area of the external genital organs. Only 48% (46 individuals) reported paying attention to these signs, while more than half — 52% (50 individuals) — either do not notice or ignore such symptoms. This may be related to both low awareness and certain barriers, such as fear of

discussing intimate topics or the lack of examples of appropriate behavior within their environment.

When respondents were asked to name the symptoms they considered characteristic of genital infections, itching or burning was the most recognizable - 79 people chose it. Next in frequency of responses is "unusual" discharge - 66 respondents indicated this symptom. Pain during intercourse was chosen by 45 respondents, pain during urination was chosen by 36 respondents, and bleeding between menstruation was noted by 46 girls, which may indicate a less deep understanding of the problem or lack of personal experience with similar symptoms. Only three of the surveyed girls noted other symptoms, which indicates a limited understanding of the variety of manifestations of infections.

Knowledge about the asymptomatic course of genital infections is also an important component of forming a responsible attitude to health. Only 47% (45 people) knew that some infections can develop unnoticed, but cause serious consequences in the future. The rest — 53% (51 people) — had no idea about this, which is a worrying sign: without such knowledge, girls may ignore preventive examinations, not realizing their importance.

The level of awareness regarding the negative impact of antibiotics on the microflora of the genitals also turned out to be insufficient. Only 41% of respondents (39 people) knew about the connection between uncontrolled or improper use of antibiotics and disruption of the microflora of the genitals, in particular candidiasis. Another 28% (27 people) completely denied such information, and 31% (30 people) replied that they had heard about it partially, which indicates a fragmentary perception of this topic.

Finally, assessing knowledge about the possibility of contracting infections not only during sexual contact, but also through non-compliance with personal hygiene rules, it was found that only 44% of respondents (42 people) fully possess this information. A third of respondents (34%, i.e. 33 people) only partially knew about this route of infection, and 22% (21 people) had no idea about it. Thus, a significant part of girls remains at risk due to the lack of basic knowledge, which emphasizes the need for systematic educational work in educational institutions and medical institutions.

Despite the fact that some girls pay attention to changes in their own bodies, the issue of seeking medical help remains quite complex and ambiguous. Among those who noticed changes in discharge from the genital tract, only 41% sought medical help. This is a positive fact, as it indicates a certain trust in medical professionals and a willingness to respond to symptoms in a timely manner. At the same time, 57% did not seek medical help, which is worrying - perhaps some girls underestimate the seriousness of such changes or feel fear, shame or barriers associated with visiting a gynecologist. Another 2% plan to seek help, but delay, which can also be risky, since valuable time for early diagnosis is lost.

A similar situation is observed in the response to the question about visiting a gynecologist in connection with suspected infections of the internal genital organs

or inflammatory processes. Only 10% of respondents (10 people) visit a doctor for this purpose. This is a very low figure, which indicates an insufficient culture of prevention and ignoring potentially dangerous conditions. Another 25% (24 people) noted that they do this very rarely, while the vast majority — 65% (62 people) — have never visited a gynecologist with a suspected genital infection. This situation is most likely due to a low level of awareness, fears, psychological barriers or difficulty in accessing medical services, especially in adolescence.

Regarding preventive examinations, the situation remains equally concerning. Only 22% of respondents (21 individuals) regularly visit a gynecologist, even if they do not have symptoms. This indicates a responsible attitude towards health; however, this percentage is clearly insufficient to ensure timely detection of pathologies. Additionally, 78% do not visit a gynecologist at all, which highlights the urgent need for educating young people about the importance of preventive examinations, especially for those who are sexually active or in adolescence, when the foundations of attitude towards their body and health are formed.

The low frequency of visits to the gynecologist, both for preventive purposes and when suspicious symptoms are present, is directly related to the level of awareness among girls about the characteristics and consequences of genital infections. The study showed that only 42% of respondents (40 individuals) are aware of the existence of bacterial, viral, and fungal forms of inflammatory diseases of the genital organs. This indicates a basic level of knowledge among some participants, but it is insufficient to form a comprehensive understanding of possible inflammatory diseases of the female reproductive system. Another 34% (33 individuals) have no knowledge of this distinction, and 24% (23 individuals) have only partial or unclear knowledge about this pathology. Such a distribution of responses points to a significant educational gap regarding gynecological diseases.

Of particular concern is that knowledge about the potential reproductive health consequences of genital infections remains limited. Only 24% of girls (23) clearly understand the link between infections and complications such as infertility or problems during pregnancy. More than half of the respondents — 51% (49) — have modest knowledge, but lack confidence or deeper knowledge, indicating a superficial level of awareness. Another 25% (24) have not heard of such a link at all, highlighting the need for targeted information to girls about the long-term health risks.

Equally important is understanding the oncological threats that can be caused by some genital infections, in particular the human papillomavirus (HPV). Only 36% (34) of respondents know that HPV can cause cervical cancer. This indicator indicates a very limited level of awareness about one of the most important topics in the field of women's health. The majority of respondents 64% are completely unaware of the connection between infections and oncological diseases, or are partially aware. Thus, most girls are not aware of the potential danger of a long asymptomatic

course of such infections and their possible consequences in the future.

In general, it can be stated that the level of awareness about the nature, transmission routes and consequences of genital infections among girls is fragmentary and insufficient. This significantly affects their attitude to their own health, prevention and timely seeking medical care.

Analyzing the survey results, we found that most respondents have basic knowledge about important preventive measures for genital infections. The most important factor for them is personal hygiene, which was emphasized by 87 respondents, who consider it an essential measure for preventing infections. This result indicates a high level of awareness of basic health principles and the necessity of maintaining hygiene and taking care of the body. Another important preventive measure is the use of barrier methods of contraception, which was noted by 76 respondents. This suggests that most girls are aware of protection against sexually transmitted infections and consider condoms an effective method of protection. However, when compared to other options, regular gynecological examinations were mentioned by 77 respondents, which is positive but indicates the need for further promotion of the importance of preventive doctor visits.

However, not all girls are fully aware of the importance of less popular, but no less effective means of prevention. Taking vitamins or probiotics was mentioned by only 39 respondents, which indicates some understanding of their importance for the body's microflora, but this option is not the main one for the majority. At the same time, only 17 respondents consider abstinence from sexual contact to be a reliable way to prevent infections, which may be due to the modern approach to sexual health, where the majority recognizes that genital infections can be transmitted not only through sexual contact.

One of the most important aspects of prevention is vaccination against the human papillomavirus (HPV), which can reduce the risk of developing oncological diseases, in particular cervical cancer. [4; 5] However, as the survey showed, only 10.4% of respondents (10 people) have already been vaccinated, which indicates that this method of prevention is not yet widespread among young people. It is positive that 26.0% (25 people) intend to get vaccinated, but the majority — 66.7% (64 people) — do not plan to do so, which indicates a serious information vacuum and underestimation of the importance of the vaccine. Among the main reasons why respondents did not get vaccinated, the most noted were lack of knowledge about the vaccine (41.7%), fears about side effects (39.6%), 12.5% consider vaccination unnecessary, and 4.2% noted that it is inaccessible to them either logistically or financially. This once

again emphasizes the importance of informing and educating young people and their parents.

Overall, while girls demonstrate awareness of basic preventive measures for genital infections, there are significant gaps in knowledge about important aspects such as HPV vaccination and a deeper understanding of preventive measures. This indicates the need for intensified educational work and access to accurate medical recommendations to ensure the health of future generations.

Conclusions

Awareness of genital infections:

- Most respondents demonstrated only a basic understanding of the symptoms of genital infections.
- 53% of respondents are unaware of the potential complications associated with genital infections.
- Only 36% of respondents are aware of the systemic impact of genital infections on the body, including their role in the development of autoimmune diseases, chronic pain syndromes, and neurological disorders.

Seeking medical help:

- 57% of respondents do not seek medical care even when experiencing pathological discharges or signs of inflammation.

Awareness about HPV and cervical cancer:

- 64% of adolescent girls are unaware of the role of HPV in the pathogenesis of cervical cancer.

Vaccination rate:

- Only 10,4% of respondents are vaccinated
- 26% plan to get vaccinated

Main reasons for refusal:

- Lack of information about the vaccine – 41,7%
- Fear of side effects – 39,6%

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